

Melting Process—A Statistical Approach*

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A partition function for a system of 'n' particles each consisting of N units and n_h holes has been used and its properties have been investigated near melting point. The internal partition function for torsional oscillations has been taken into account. It is found that in addition to the contributions to the heat of melting due to mixing of rotational isomers and torsional oscillations, a significant contribution is made due to introduction of highly mobile holes. The heat of melting, H_m has been calculated for normal alkanes, normal alcohols, fatty acids, polymethylene, polypropene, poly 1-butene and polyvinyl chloride and compared to the available experimental data. The agreement between theory and experiment is fair.

The transition from solid to liquid results in a sudden increase in all transport properties. For most solids the process of melting is accompanied by an increase in volume. Another important factor to be considered is the effect of pressure on melting temperature. It has been suggested that the solid-fluid transition can occur at any temperature under high enough pressure. Gases such as hydrogen and helium can be solidified at temperatures many times the critical temperature T_c . The melting curve of helium can be approximately given by $pm\alpha T^{3/2}$. Since the minimum value of the intermolecular potential is approximately kT_c for all gases, and helium can be solidified at temperature at least $10 T_c$, it can be reasonably concluded that at least at high pressures the attractive forces are of less importance and the sharp repulsive forces are responsible for solid-fluid transition.

At present there does not exist any satisfactory quantitative theory of melting even for simple monoatomic fluids. As such the general problem of phase transition remains an unsolved problem of equilibrium statistical mechanics. Further the phase transitions are general phenomena and as such admit only general explanations. The approximate theories developed so far are based on a search for an instability of one of the phases, which is generally regarded as an indication of the end of possible metastable state. For solid-liquid transitions, the instability may be sought for either in (a) the solid phase or in (b) liquid phase.

Lindemann considers that instability in any (mono-atomic) solid is introduced when the amplitude of vibration of an atom or an ion reaches a certain fraction of the lattice parameter. The predicted value of melting temperatures based on this simple concept agreed with experimental values within $\pm 20\%$ for simple substances. Moreover, this approach does not depend upon any property of liquid phase.

* Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

Instability in a liquid may result due to abrupt ordering. To consider this phenomenon it is usual to assume a mathematical model. For this purpose, at normal pressure a liquid can be considered as a fluid of hard spheres perturbed by the attractive part of the intermolecular potential. For some of the integral equations for the pair correlation function in a liquid the solution becomes of a long range oscillatory character. This is regarded as the onset of instability in the system. These involved mathematical treatments, however, show inadequate agreement with experimental results.

A better approach may consist of taking into account the properties of both the phases. Thus, it may be assumed that in liquid the gaseous and solid phases co-exist at sub-microscopic dispersion level in equilibrium with each other giving rise to unusual transport properties. This approach must also rationalise the dependence of melting temperature on pressure, both at lower and higher values.

Assuming that statistical mechanics alone can explain the phenomena of phase transitions without using other special arguments, one has to obtain a sharp transition like melting by this method. The n -particle canonical partition function is an analytic function of thermodynamic variables and is strictly positive. Taking a logarithm does not introduce a singularity. Therefore, the discontinuities and singularities can occur when the various quantities per particle or unit are considered and then the limit of $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $V \rightarrow \infty$ are imposed, while the local properties are kept constant. In short, some kind of thermodynamic limits are imposed on the mathematical construct and both discontinuity and singularity can be introduced for an n -particle partition function.

THEORETICAL

An attempt has been made to obtain an n -particle Walter-Eyring type partition function for single component system in which the properties of two phases have been taken into consideration to calculate the heat of melting of n -alkanes, n -alcohols and monobasic fatty acids. This approach based on realistic assumptions is likely to yield better agreement with experiment than a purely mathematical construct. In the following, the statistical approach to melting developed by Flory¹ considering rotational isomerism of polymer chains and modified by Volkenstein and Ptitsyn², is further modified to take into considerations a sudden change in the transport properties due to thermal fluctuations on melting. The following assumptions have been made with a view to achieving a realistic semblance with the real systems.

1. The long chain molecules in crystalline state i.e., before melting are assumed to be in trans-rotational isomeric state on a lattice.
2. The trans isomer is assumed to execute harmonic torsional oscillations with frequency w , while the coiled isomers execute the same torsional oscillations with frequency w' .
3. The lattice consists of chain molecules as well as holes. Before melting the few holes are frozen in lattice in a manner which gives the lattice characteristic of crystalline state. These holes are there due to purely spatial requirements of a crystalline lattice. This is valid even just before melting process commences. On melting at $T = T_m$ these

holes acquire gas molecules like mobility, thereby resulting in a sudden increase of transport properties of the lattice. One can not rule out the introduction of fresh holes on melting.

To be realistic it is difficult to construct a wholly crystalline lattice except at absolute zero. For long chain molecules the concept of crystallinity can never be absolute, the partial amorphosity of the chain may be enough to introduce enough number of holes just before melting even if no increase in volume is permitted on melting. The meaning of $n_h = 0$, in crystalline state has more to do with denied translational freedom to these holes before melting than to their existence. Unless these holes are mobile their existence can not be perceived, due to negligible translations. Therefore, f_g has meaning only at and above $T = T_m$.

Definitions of the various symbols used are given below :

- n = Number of linear chain molecules per mole,
 N = number of segments per chain molecule,
 n_h = number of holes per mole of chain molecules,
 γ = coordinations number of a cell in lattice,
 V_0 = molar volume of n chains in (trans) crystalline state,
 $V - V_0$ = volume occupied by n_h holes or gas like cells per mole of liquid,
 E_s = potential energy of solid per molecule,
 f = chain flexibility per molecule,
 f_s = partition function of solid like equilibrium positions,
 f_g = partition function per gas like equilibrium position,
 ω = frequency of torsional oscillations for (crystalline) trans isomer in cm^{-1} ,
 ω' = frequency of torsional oscillations per coiled isomer in cm^{-1} ,
 ϵ_i = $i \frac{hc\omega}{2\pi}$,
 ϵ'_j = $j \frac{hc\omega'}{2\pi} + \Delta U$
 ΔU = excess energy over trans isomer (crystalline) per coiled chain molecule,
 C_t = fraction of trans-isomer in the oscillation level; $\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} C_t = 1$,
 C'_j = fraction of coiled isomer in the j th oscillational level; $\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j = 1$,

and

$$\delta = \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^2 = \text{a volume dependent parameter.}$$

It is reasonable to assume that the most probable configuration will be the one in which the molecules are distributed between the two types of equilibrium positions in the ratio of V_0/V (crystalline) and $(V-V_0)/V$ (gaseous state). Then the complete Walter-Eyring^{2*} type partition function for nN segment is given by (1).

$$F = (f_s \exp -E_s/KT)^{V_0/V} (f_g^{nN(1-f)} \exp -\delta E_s/KT) \frac{V-V_0}{V} \frac{(Nn+n_h)!}{Nn! n_h!} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{where } f_s = q_1^{n_h} q^n \frac{\{(n_h+Nn)! (n_h+Nn)^{-n(N-1)}\}}{n_h! n! 2^n} \frac{\gamma^n (\gamma-2)^{fn(N-2)} \{n(N-2)\}!}{\prod_{i=0}^{\infty} [(1-f)n(N-2)C_i]! \prod_{j=0}^{\infty} [fn(N-2)C'_j]!} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$f_g = \frac{(2\pi mKT)^{3/2}}{h^3} \quad \dots (3)$$

No internal partition function has been assigned to holes.

$$Z = \left[q_1^{n_h} \frac{q^n (n_h+Nn)! (n_h+Nn)^{-n(N-1)} \gamma^n (\gamma-2)^{fn(N-2)} \{n(N-2)\}!}{n_h! n! 2^n \prod_{i=0}^{\infty} [(1-f)n(N-2)C_i]! \prod_{j=0}^{\infty} [fn(N-2)C'_j]!} \right. \\ \left. \text{Exp} \left\{ \frac{1}{KT} \left[-(1-f)n(N-2) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} C_i \epsilon_i - fn(N-2) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j \epsilon'_j - \frac{Nn n_h KT}{n_h+Nn} \right] \right\}^{V_0/V} \right. \\ \left. \left[\left\{ \frac{(2\pi mKT)^{3/2}}{h^3} \right\}^{nN(1-f)} \text{Exp} -\delta E_s /KT \right] \frac{V-V_0}{V} \frac{(Nn+n_h)!}{Nn! n_h!} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\ln Z = \frac{V_0}{V} \left[n_h \ln q_1 + n \ln q + (n_h+Nn) \ln (n_h+Nn) - (n_h+Nn) - n(N-1) \ln (n_h+Nn) \right. \\ \left. - n_h \ln n_h + n_h - n_h \ln n + n - n \ln 2 + n \ln \gamma + fn(N-2) \ln (\gamma-2) \right. \\ \left. + n(N-2) \ln n(N-2) - n(N-2) + fn(N-2) - fn(N-2) \ln fn(N-2) \right. \\ \left. - fn(N-2) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j \ln C'_j - (1-f)n(N-2) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} C_i \ln C_i + (1-f)n(N-2) \right. \\ \left. - (1-f)n(N-2) \ln (1-f)n(N-2) + \frac{1}{KT} \left\{ -(1-f)n(N-2) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} C_i \epsilon_i \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - fn(N-2) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j \epsilon'_j - \frac{Nn n_h KT}{n_h+Nn} \right\} \right] + \frac{V-V_0}{V} \left\{ \frac{3}{2} nN(1-f) \ln 2\pi mKT \right. \\ \left. - 3nN(1-f) \ln h - \frac{\delta E_s}{KT} \right\} + \{(Nn+n_h) \ln (Nn+n_h) + (Nn+n_h) - Nn \ln Nn \\ + Nn - n_h \ln n_h + n_h\} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$-E_s = \left[-(1-f)n(N-2) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} C_i \epsilon_i - fn(N-2) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j \epsilon'_j - \frac{Nn n_h KT}{n_h+Nn} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

The coefficients C_i and C_j and f can be obtained by differentiating $\ln Z$ with respect to C_i , C'_j and f and setting the resultant equal to zero.

This yields,

$$C_i = e^{-\left[1 + \frac{\epsilon_i}{KT} - \frac{\delta\epsilon_i}{KT} + \frac{\delta\epsilon_i}{KT} \frac{V}{V_0}\right]} \quad \dots (7)$$

and

$$C'_j = e^{-\left[1 + \frac{\epsilon'_j}{KT} - \frac{\delta\epsilon'_j}{KT} + \frac{\delta\epsilon'_j}{KT} \frac{V}{V_0}\right]} \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$f = 2e^{\frac{-\Delta U/KT}{(1+2e^{-\Delta U/KT})}} \text{ by setting } (2\pi mKT)^{3/2} \approx h^3 \text{ approximately} \quad \dots (9)$$

The heat of melting is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H_m &= -KT^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{KT} \right) \\ \Delta\phi &= -KT \ln Z \end{aligned} \quad \dots (10)$$

Since at melting point i.e., at $T = T_m$, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H_m &= \left[(1-f)n(N-2) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} C_i \epsilon_i + fn(N-2) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} C'_j \epsilon'_j \right] \left[\frac{V_0}{V} - \frac{V-V_0}{V} \delta \right] \\ &\quad + \left[\frac{3}{2} NRT_m \left(\frac{V-V_0}{V} \right) (1-f) \right] \end{aligned} \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left[\frac{(N-2) \frac{nhC\omega}{2\pi} e^{-\frac{hcw}{2\pi} \alpha}}{\left(1 - e^{-\frac{hcw}{2\pi} \alpha}\right)} + fn(N-2)(\Delta U) \right] \left[\frac{V_0}{V} - \frac{V-V_0}{V} \delta \right] \\ &\quad + \left[-\frac{3}{2} NRT_m \left(\frac{V-V_0}{V} \right) (1-f) \right] \end{aligned} \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\text{where} \quad \alpha = \left[\frac{1}{KT_m} - \frac{\delta}{KT_m} + \frac{\delta}{KT_m} \frac{V}{V_0} \right] \quad \dots (13)$$

For short chains $f = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H_m &= \left[\frac{(N-2) \frac{nhC\omega}{2\pi} e^{-\frac{hcw}{2\pi} \alpha}}{\left(1 - e^{-\frac{hcw}{2\pi} \alpha}\right)} \right] \left[\frac{V_0}{V} - \frac{V-V_0}{V} \delta \right] + \left[\frac{3}{2} NRT_m \left(\frac{V-V_0}{V} \right) \right] \\ &\quad \dots (14) \end{aligned}$$

Heat of melting per unit for long chains can be calculated by dividing with N , with the assumption that $N \gg 1$.

Thus,

$$\Delta H_m = \left[\frac{\frac{nhc\omega}{2\pi} e^{-\frac{hc\omega}{2\pi} \alpha}}{1 - e^{-\frac{hc\omega}{2\pi} \alpha}} + fn(\Delta U) \right] \left[\frac{V_0}{V} - \frac{V - V_0}{V} \delta \right] + \frac{3}{2} NRT_m \frac{(V - V_0)}{V} \quad (1-f) \quad \dots (15)$$

Comparison of Experimental and Calculated Values of Heat melting: A test of the validity of equation (14) lies in comparing the calculated values of ΔH_m with those obtained experimentally.

Fig. 1. Heat of melting for n -Alkanes v/s number of C-atoms.

--Δ-- Δ -- Theoretical Curve.
 —O— O — Experimental curve

Two types of cases may arise; those for which the number $N \gg 1$ i.e., long chain molecules for which the value of $f > 0$ and those for which N is small and $f = 0$.

Case I :— $N \gg 1, f > 0$

Table 1 gives a comparison of the theoretically calculated values of ΔH_m (cals per monomer unit) and experimentally observed values for polymethylene, polypropene (Isotactic), Poly 1-Butene and Polyvinyl chloride for which all the parameters required in (15) are available. The calculations have been made on the assumption that $V_0/V = 1/10$, which is quite realistic for small non-Polar molecules.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Name of the Polymer	T_m °K	ω cm ⁻¹	ΔU cal/mole	Calculated ΔH_m cal/monomer unit, % rotisomer of tor. osc. + thermal	Experimentally observed ΔH_m cal/monomer unit
1.	Polymethylene (-CH ₂ -) _n	410.00 ⁽³⁾	270 ⁽⁷⁾	800	727.16 4.3% + 8.65% + 85.05%	920.00 ⁽¹⁰⁾
2.	Polypropene CH ₃ (CH-CH ₂) _n	451.00 ⁽⁴⁾	200 ⁽⁸⁾	1950 ⁽⁶⁾	2167.12 3.2% + 6.5% + 91.3%	2400.00 ⁽¹¹⁾
3.	Poly-1-Butene C ₂ H ₅ (-CH-CH ₂ -) _n	408.00 ⁽⁵⁾	200 ⁽⁸⁾	1950 ⁽⁶⁾	2042.36 2.69% + 6.26% + 91.05%	1680.00 ⁽⁶⁾
4.	Polyvinyl Chloride (-CH ₂ -CHCl-) _n	546.00 ⁽⁶⁾	236 ⁽⁹⁾	4470 ⁽⁹⁾	3055.90 0.82% + 5.68% + 93.5%	2700.00 ⁽⁶⁾

It can be easily seen that percentage contribution due to mixing of rotational isomers is the least, followed by a small contribution from torsional oscillations. The major contribution is due to the introduction of mobile holes in the lattice on melting.

Case II : $2 < N \leq 12$ and $f = 0$.

For short chains, it is reasonable to assume as a first approximation that the flexibility $f = 0$.

n-alkanes : It can be seen from Table 2(A) that for *n*-alkanes the agreement between the calculated and experimentally observed values is fair. The higher calculated values

TABLE 2(A)

Values of ΔH_m for *n*-Alkanes

No. of C-atoms	Substance	Chemical Formula	Melting Pt. T_m °K	Theoretically calculated ΔH_m cal/mole	Experimental value of ΔH_m cal/mole
3	<i>n</i> -Propane	C ₃ H ₈	85.9 ⁽¹²⁾	705.45	840.84 ⁽²¹⁾
4	<i>n</i> -Butane	C ₄ H ₁₀	134.6 ⁽¹³⁾	1486.60	1120.80 ⁽²¹⁾
5	<i>n</i> -Pentane	C ₅ H ₁₂	143.3 ⁽¹⁴⁾	1990.90	2008.08 ⁽²²⁾
6	<i>n</i> -Hexane	C ₆ H ₁₄	179.0 ⁽¹⁵⁾	2997.40	3019.22 ⁽²³⁾
7	<i>n</i> -Heptane	C ₇ H ₁₆	182.5 ⁽¹⁶⁾	3575.35	3378.00 ⁽²⁴⁾
8	<i>n</i> -Octane	C ₈ H ₁₈	216.2 ⁽¹⁷⁾	4854.72	4925.94 ⁽²⁵⁾
9	<i>n</i> -Nonane	C ₉ H ₂₀	219.5 ⁽¹⁸⁾	5552.95	*
10	<i>n</i> -Decane	C ₁₀ H ₂₂	243.3 ⁽¹⁸⁾	6849.90	6864.28 ⁽²⁵⁾
11	<i>n</i> -Undecane	C ₁₁ H ₂₄	247.4 ⁽¹⁹⁾	7670.88	*
12	<i>n</i> -Dodecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	263.3 ⁽²⁰⁾	8916.92	8726.10 ⁽²⁵⁾

* Data not available

of ΔH_m as compared to experimental ones for higher alkanes can be conveniently traced to the assumption $f = 0$. As the chain length increases, the degree of flexibility is bound to increase and the break-down of the assumption $f = 0$, is obvious. However, it is not possible to assign an unambiguous value to f for short chain alkanes.

n-alcohols : Table 2(B). The values of ΔH_m have been calculated upto Decylalcohol. However, only a few experimental values are available and these are found to be in fair agreement with the theoretically calculated values.

TABLE 2(B)

Values of ΔH_m for n-aliphatic alcohols

N	Substance	Chemical formula	Melting Pt. T_m °K	Theoretically calculated ΔH_m cal/mole	Experimental value of ΔH_m cal/mole
3	Propyl Alcohol	C ₃ H ₇ OH	146.9 ⁽²⁶⁾	1208.7	1239.6 ⁽²⁶⁾
4	Butyl Alcohol	C ₄ H ₉ OH	183.2 ⁽²⁷⁾	2028.5	2214.8 ⁽³²⁾
5	Amyl Alcohol	C ₅ H ₁₁ OH	194.1 ⁽²⁸⁾	2701.0	*
6	Hexyl Alcohol	C ₆ H ₁₃ OH	226.0 ⁽²⁷⁾	3789.2	3672.0 ⁽³³⁾
7	Heptyl Alcohol	C ₇ H ₁₅ OH	238.0 ⁽²⁹⁾	4675.6	*
8	Octyl Alcohol	C ₈ H ₁₇ OH	256.3 ⁽³⁰⁾	5800.4	*
10	Decyl Alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ OH	280.0 ⁽³¹⁾	7887.1	*

* Data not available.

n-fatty acids : Table 3. The absence of experimentally observed values of ΔH_m , except for few cases made it necessary to evaluate these using Clausius-Claypeyron equation :

$$\frac{dP}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H_m}{T(V_l - V_s)}$$

where the value of (dP/dT) was obtained graphically using the data available in literature. The evaluation of $(V_l - V_s)$, i.e., the increase in volume on melting was not readily available.

TABLE 3

Comparison between theoretically calculated and graphically calculated values of ΔH_m of N-monocarboxylic fatty acids

N	Name of the acid	Melting Pt. °K	dp/dT cal/cc/K°	Extrapolated density at T_m gms/cc	ΔH_m Theoret. calculated cal/mole	ΔH_m Graphical cal/mole
3	Propionic Acid	252.2 ⁽³⁴⁾	1.16 ⁽³⁴⁾	1.1038 ⁽³⁵⁾	2080.94	2090.00
4	Butyric Acid	267.5 ⁽³⁴⁾	1.225 ⁽³⁴⁾	0.9835 ⁽³⁶⁾	2970.35	2940.00
5	Valeric Acid	238.5 ⁽³⁷⁾	1.330 ⁽³⁴⁾	0.9880 ⁽³⁸⁾	3327.90	3146.00
6	Caproic Acid	269.40 ⁽³⁹⁾	1.231 ⁽³⁴⁾	0.9474 ⁽⁴⁰⁾	4507.00	4060.00
7	Heptanoic Acid	265.50 ⁽⁴¹⁾	1.330 ⁽³⁴⁾	0.9410 ⁽⁴¹⁾	5208.20	4880.00
8	Caprylic Acid	289.3 ⁽⁴²⁾	1.10 ⁽³⁴⁾	0.9114 ⁽⁴³⁾	6490.00	5000.00

The molar volume V_l was obtained by extrapolation of density values. The volume V_s occupied by solid cannot be equated to V_0 , the volume occupied at $T = 0^\circ\text{K}$. Thus, a reasonably convenient assumption correlating $(V_l - V_s)$ to V is required. For *n*-fatty acids

it has been assumed that $(V_l - V_s)/V = 1/10$. The evaluated values of ΔH_m are correct within the limit of validity of this assumption. The comparison made between experimental and calculated values for *n*-fatty acids are to be viewed within these limitations.

Concluding Remarks: An analysis of the data on the molar heat of melting, both experimental and theoretical indicates that the present attempt has the possibility of generalization. The tendency to deviate from experimentally observed values as the chain length increases can be conveniently ascribed to the neglect of flexibility of the chain.

One of the main features of the present attempt is the realization of the important role played by the introduction of mobile holes on melting. It is obvious that the major contribution to the transport properties comes from the highly increased mobility of holes in the lattice due to melting. It may be argued that it is an artificial mathematical construct. Even if it is so, the fair agreements observed for the number of systems investigated could not be just fortuitous. The comparison of larger number of experimental data with the theoretical expectations is in progress.

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